

Primary Intraosseous Cavernous and Epithelioid Hemangioma (PICH); Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Intraosseous hemangiomas of the skull are rare benign vascular tumors that represent approximately 0.2% of all bone tumors and 10% of benign skull tumors. We present a rare case of intraosseous hemangioma in 54-year-old man who presented a lesion in the lower third of the clivus, it was sent for intraoperative study and the squash smear showed a vascular lesion with eosinophilic epithelioid cells that was deferred for definitive study. Subsequently, tissue was sent showing bone spicules with capillaries and epithelioid endothelial cells proliferation. Which were intensely positive for CD31, CD34 and VEGF. It was diagnosed as intraosseous mixed and epithelioid Hemangioma. The patient bled considerably during the postoperative period and died of hypovolemic shock.

Keywords: Cavernoma; Cavernous hemangioma; Epithelioid hemangioma; Skull tumors; Intraoperative analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Hemangiomas are a histologically benign vascular tumor, which is divided into 3 types: capillary, cavernous, depending on the dominant vessels, although mixed forms exist. The capillary type is composed of circumscribed proliferation of predominantly small capillary sized blood vessels, rich in small vascular lumina's lacking fibrous septa^[1]. The Cavernous hemangioma (CH) consists of clusters of dilated blood vessels, which

are detached by fibrous septa. Most cases arise in children, and are superficial lesions and commonly in head and neck region localization, presented with equal gender distribution and recurrence is uncommon and only exceptional cases showing malignant transformation. The epithelioid type forming by clusters of dilated blood vessels with evidence epithelioid endothelial cells^[1,2].

Skeletal or bone hemangiomas are radiology highly nonspecific and usually not diagnosed as such, they are uncommon tumors, accounting for 0.7 to 1 percent of all bone neoplasms^[1].

Primary intraosseous cavernous hemangiomas (PICHs) are a rare bone tumor^[2]. These tumors, arising from the intrinsic vasculature of the bone, are mostly found in vertebral bodies and represent 0.2 percent of all benign neoplasms of the skull. Its presence in the skull is exceedingly rare, with only a few cases being reported worldwide^[1]. Despite their low frequency, cavernous hemangiomas must be comprised in the differential diagnosis of slow-growing osteolytic lesions located within the skull. The majority of these lesions reported have been asymptomatic, but patients can present with focal pain or a palpable mass^[2].

PICHs are usually found in the vertebral column and rarely seen in the skulls. The earliest description of skull PICH was in 1845 by Toynbee^[3].

Epithelioid hemangioma (EH) is an extremely rare intracranial tumor and is regarded as a low-proliferation tumor could it exhibits some clinically malignant behaviors, such as local invasion, recurrence and metastasis.

In this work we presented a case report an intraosseous epithelioid cavernous hemangioma in the in a 54-year-old man. Who was initially suspected of a vascular event and through imaging studies suggested a clivus chordoma.

CLINICAL PRESENTATION

54-year-old man, merchant, with alcoholism and smoking for 30 years. He started with paresthesia of the tongue that was managed with thiamine, later he presented occipital headaches that were treated with analgesics, later dysphagia to solids and liquids, dysphonia and difficulty breathing were added. Physical examination shows tongue with dysarthria, facial symmetry, with decreased gag reflexes, left buccal cord paralysis, hypotrophies of the lingual muscles, left hemicorporal hypoesthesia, involvement of left IX, X, XI and XII nerves. Suspecting a probable medial and lateral bulbar cerebral infarction. The CT scan was performed showing a hypointense lesion in the brain stem (**Figure 1**) and, suggesting a probable clivus chordoma, and surgery was performed with an extended transnasal endoscopic, far medial and extreme medial approach, during the surgery we found a lytic bone tumor with retrocarotid and parapharyngeal extension, we finally made a gross total resection, with intraoperative bleeding of 1,600 ml. Tissue is sent for intraoperative squash smears cytology study, was stained with hematoxylin and eosin. The smears showed structures suggesting blood vessels, with occasional clear-looking eosinophilic cells with epithelioid appearance in a hemorrhagic, necrotic background (**Figure 2**). Chordoma was clinically suspected and the presence of these cells did not confirm the diagnosis, so it was deferred to a definitive study. Subsequently, tissue was received that measured 2x2cm. Reddish hemorrhagic

that presented bone spicules. Histologically, these bone spicules were observed, among them a benign neoplasm formed by capillary vessels was identified. In some vessels, these clear cells observed in the intraoperative study were crowded at one of the ends of the vessels (Figure 3). Immunohistochemical staining was performed and these cells described above were CD32, CD34 Fli1 and FVIII positive reaction, and EMA cytokeratin were negative immunoreaction (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Magnetic resonance imaging of the skull with contrast medium. It is observed in topography of the clivus, with a predominance of the left side, an image with an irregular shape, with poorly defined margins, which conditions remodeling, expansion and areas of destruction of the cortical medulla. It has a discretely heterogeneous behavior, predominantly hypointense on T1 with fat saturation (a) and FLAIR (b); hyperintense on T2 (c), with images of a cystic appearance inside; presents some irregular areas of signal deviation in gradient echo (d); It does not restrict diffusion (e and f) and after contrast administration it has heterogeneous enhancement. It presents extension towards the anterior part of the foramen magnum, the predominantly left occipital condyles, the anterior perivertebral space, the petrous portion of the temporal bone and the cistern of the left cerebellopontine angle. With approximate dimensions of 62x26x40 mm in the laterolateral, dorsoventral and rostrocaudal axes.

Figure 2: Shows the squash cytology in the intraoperative diagnosis. (a) the squash smear shows a hemorrhagic background, with structures that resemble blood vessels (H&E x200), surrounded by a thin layer of endothelial cells, some of them larger in size (c) being observed nests of cells with the appearance of large cells and in (d) we observe cells with eosinophilic cytoplasm with an epithelioid appearance (H&Ex400).

Figure 3: Histologically a bone lesion is observed, (a) and (b) bone spicules are observed among which proliferation richly vascularized with thickened-wall vessels and turgid endothelium. are focally a vessel with endothelial cell hyperplasia (H&Ex200) is observed, (c) the image It shows giant cells of the osteoblast type among the globular cells with abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm, cells with an epithelial appearance. (d) hyperplasia of endothelial cells with an epithelial appearance is observed. The arrows show the epithelial cells with an epithelial appearance (H&Ex400). Immunohistochemistry shows positivity for FVIII in (e), CD31 in (f), CD34 in (g) and Fli1 in (g) in the endothelial cells (IHC x400).

Based on the histological and immunohistochemical findings, the diagnosis of intraosseous epithelioid cavernous hemangioma was made. The patient bleeding considerably during the surgery for which he was suspended and went to intensive care where he developed pneumonia and 3 days later, he died. No autopsy study was performed.

DISCUSSION

PICs are most frequently involving the vertebrae site, and hemangiomas of the calvarial bones account for 0.2 percent of all bone neoplasms and seldom in the skull base^[4]. Women are two times more commonly afflicted than are men and the peak age incidence is the fourth decade^[5], while pediatric cases also have been reported^[5]. The great majority of cases reported of hemangiomas are unifocal lesions but multiple hemangiomas have been reported.

Alexiou GA et al^[6] carried out a bibliometric study and 51 studies with 77 patients; the mean age of the patients was 32.7 years with a female predominance of 1.4:1. The majority of cranial PICs were located in the calvarium, primarily in the frontal and parietal regions, with only a few cases were located in the skull base^[5,6]. In another review carried out by Park H et al^[7] they studied a series of 93 cases of skull PIC reported in previous literatures from 1845 to 2015, of which 44.1 were located in the frontal bone, 12.9% involved the temporal bones, 11.8% occurred in the occipital bone, 12.9% in parietal bone, and 5.4% in Cranial fossa; fewer cases have been reported in sphenoid, zygomatic, ethmoid, clivus, and orbital rim^[7], etc. PIC is mostly seen in middle age and the male-to-female ratio ranges from 3:1 to 2:1.2. The pathogenesis of PIC remains unknown. Trauma May also has an important role in etiopathology^[7].

The characteristic image consists of a well-defined, oval or rounded lytic lesion, with trabeculae radiating from a common center within it^[5]. On MRI, the lesion is usually of mixed intensity, predominantly isointense or hyperintense on T1 sequence, hyperintense on T2, and with contrast enhancement after the administration of Gadolinium^[5,8]. however, they are diagnosed as tumors and the finally diagnosis is generally histological analysis, spited their low frequency, cavernous hemangiomas must be included in the differential diagnosis of slow-growing osteolytic lesions located within the skull^[5].

The clinical and radiological differential diagnosis includes other slowly growing expansive bone lesions, versus osteolytic lesions that include osteoma, aneurysmal bone cyst, giant cell tumor, fibrous dysplasia, sarcoma, meningioma, metastasis, Paget's disease, dermoid cyst, and multiple myeloma and/or any other type of

tumor^[5,8]. The growth pattern of these tumors is usually exophytic, although cases with intracranial extension have been described, which may be associated with epidural or subdural bleeding^[4].

In this case, the intraoperative diagnosis of this lesion was not specific, suspecting chordoma and the presence of large, fine eosinophilic cytoplasm cells with epithelioid appearance could have made a clear diagnosis of chordoma, however, given the presence of blood vessels we could have made the diagnosis of hemangioma. However, this condition was not considered. In general, intraoperative study of vascular lesions is not recommended. Deeply situated cellular hemangiomas may pose a difficult diagnostic challenge to the clinical as well as to the radiologist imaging.

Cytologically, cells released in third are observed that confuse the diagnosis with sarcomatous neoplasia, the endothelial cells could be in a highly vascularized area close to the tumor and create diagnostic errors^[9]. EH is observed by cohesive cells with an epithelioid appearance with abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm, a central nucleus with small nucleoli, blood vessels or vascular channels in an abortive form^[9,10]. However, immunohistochemical stains for CD34 and V81 confirm the diagnosis^[10,11].

EH is a benign vascular neoplasm consisting of a vascular proliferation with diffuse or lobular pattern and features vascular spaces lined by epithelioid endothelial cells with numerous lymphocytes and eosinophils^[11]. The inflammatory infiltrate with admixed eosinophils is usually FOS-B positive expression.

Epithelioid hemangioma (EH) is a rare tumor that can have bone involvement. Its clinically and radiographically aggressive appearance mimics a malignant neoplasm. The histological differential diagnosis including; including EH and EHE at the benign/low-grade end of the spectrum, and epithelioid angiosarcoma at the histological high-grade. the EHE shows Neoplastic epithelioid cells with round nucleus and occasionally appeared pleomorphic with evident nucleolus and eosinophilic cytoplasm, which had cytoplasmic vacuoles. In immunohistochemical stains, neoplastic cells reacted to vascular markers (CD31 and CD34), though they are negative to mesothelial markers (panCK, AE1/AE3, Ck 5/6, EMA, calretinin, WT1), TTF1, Napsin, and estrogen receptors^[12,13] Historically, the classification of vascular tumors has been heavily dependent on the clinical background and histological features, as immunohistochemical markers^[12].

HE also known as ALHE, and also angiolymphoid hyperplasia with eosinophilia^[12]. This rare condition commonly presents in middle-aged adults as discrete skin lesions and clusters as papules, plaques, and nodules in the head and neck region with a slight female preponderance in periauricular lesions. The pathogenesis of ALHE remains unclear. It is considered as rare benign vasoproliferative disease of unknown etiology. As well as, it has been considered it to be a late stage of Kimura disease. Some authors considered ALHE as a neoplasm that develops from endothelial cells; others suggest that it is secondary to an inflammatory vascular reaction secondary to complex immunological mechanisms. Other hypotheses involving environmental factors such as insect bites, trauma, and infections^[9]. The differential diagnosis included an aneurysmal bone cyst, keratinous cyst, leptomeningeal cyst and intraosseous hemangioma. While an epithelial lining was verified, the exact nature of the cyst might not be explained contempt immunohistochemical^[12,13].

EH is a rare condition with challenging diagnosis and treatment. Despite the benignity of this disease, it poses a therapeutic dilemma due to aesthetic defects and recurrence after treatment^[9].

Preoperative embolization, aiming to minimize intraoperative blood loss, was performed in the case of large tumors. The treatment of choice for cranial cavernous hemangiomas is inblock resection of the lesion, including a circumferential margin of healthy bone. The elective treatment of these tumors comprises a complete resection by craniectomy, with safe bony margins. The extended transnasal approach is a useful tool to be able to resect tumors that do not extend beyond the surgical margin, in order to avoid larger surgical approaches that could harm the patient's quality of life. In this case, it is a useful tool to combine with other types of approaches to be able to resect as much of the tumor as possible. This technique avoids unnecessary intratumoral manipulation, which carries a risk of profuse bleeding in the case of large lesions. On the other hand, the possibility of recurrence is avoided by including a safety margin [6, 7]. Radiotherapy is considered for unresectable lesions or in the case of recurrent tumors. This therapeutic modality stops tumor growth and reduces its vascularization, but does not modify the size of the lesion and carries the risk of malignancy or appearance of de novo malignancies^[6,7]. Preoperative feeding-artery embolization is recommended aiming to minimize intraoperative blood loss, but if it is an intraoperative finding; the bleeding can be fatal and complete surgery cannot always be carried out.

CONCLUSION

we reported a rare case of clivus lesion radiologically diagnosed as chordoma, surgery was performed and the specimen sent for intraoperative study, showing necrosis, hemorrhage and few eosinophilic cytoplasmic cells with epithelial appearance. In case of doubt, it was not reported as chordoma, in the study Histopathology showed an intraosseous lesion with dilated vessels and focally some showed hypertrophy of endothelial cells with an epithelioid appearance. Cavernous and epithelioid hemangioma was diagnosed. This is a rare brain condition and the first case reported with an intraoperative study.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

Written consent was obtained from the patient(s) for their anonymized information to be published in this article.

ABBREVIATIONS

Cavernous hemangiomas (CHs)

Primary intraosseous cavernous hemangiomas (PICHs)

Epithelioid hemangioma (EH)

Epithelioid Hemangioendothelioma (EHE)

REFERENCES

1. Carrasco-Moro R, García-Navarrete E, Navas-García M, Adrados de Llano M, García de Sola R. Cavernous hemangioma of the skull. Neurocirugia (Astur). 2009;20(6):559-562.
2. Nasser K, Hayashi N, Kurosaki K, et al. Intraosseous cavernous hemangioma of the frontal bone. Neurol Med Chir (Tokyo). 2007;47(11):506-508.
3. Toynbee J. An account of two vascular tumors developed in the substance of bone. *Lancet*. 1845;2:676.
4. Gottfried ON, Gluf WM, Schimdt MH. Cavernous hemangioma of the skull presenting with subdural hematoma. Neurosurg Focus. 2004;17(4):1-4.
5. Heckl S, Aschoff A, Kunze S. Cavernomas of the skull: review of the literature 1975-2000. Neurosurg Rev. 2002;25(2):56-62.
6. Alexiou GA, Lampros M, Gavra MM, Vlachos N, Ydreos J, Boviatsis EJ. Primary Intraosseous Cavernous Hemangioma of the Cranium: A Systematic Review of the Literature. World Neurosurg. 2022;164:323-329.
7. Park BH, Hwang E, Kim CH. Primary intraosseous hemangioma in the frontal bone. Arch Plast Surg. 2013;40:283-285.
8. Suzuki, Y, Ikeda H, Mutsamoto K. Neuroradiological features of intraosseous cavernous hemangioma. Neurol Med Chir. 2001;41(5):279-282.
9. Erhard CA, Vesoulis Z, Kashkari S. Fine needle aspiration cytology of cellular hemangioma of infancy. A case reports. Acta Cytol. 2000;44(6):1090-1094.
10. Baehner F, Sudilovsky D. Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology of Intraoral Epithelioid Hemangioma: A Report of Two Cases Case. Acta Cytologica. 2003;47(2):275-280.
11. Rauschenbach L, Santos AN, Dinger TF, et al. Predictive Value of Intraoperative Neuromonitoring in Brainstem Cavernous Malformation Surgery. World Neurosurg. 2021;156:e359-e373.
12. Zheng J, Liu L, Wang J, Wang S, Cao Y, Zhao JJ. Primary intracranial epithelioid hemangioendothelioma: a low-proliferation tumor exhibiting clinically malignant behavior. Neurooncol. 2012;110(1):119-127.
13. Calderaro J, Guedj N, Dauzac C, Wassef M, Guigui P, Bedossa P. A case of epithelioid hemangioma of the spine. Ann Pathol. 2011;31(4):312-315.